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Parameter extraction of the Cole-impedance model for in-situ monitoring of electrochemical sources

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ABSTRACT

An important application of equivalent electrical circuit modeling is in Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) analysis. Reliable and accurate parameter estimation of such circuits allows for identifying the source of impedance changes, which can be significant for condition monitoring of electrochemical sources in various industrial applications. The time delay between measurements and maintenance action can be reduced with in-situ parameter estimation, followed by decision-making. A method for estimating parameters of the Cole-impedance model is presented in this paper. The method can be used in modeling the impedance of batteries, fuel cells, and solar cells. Our method has been first validated using synthetic datasets, and by comparison with the relevant references. Relative errors in the case of noiseless synthetic data were lower than 0.1 %. Moreover, we processed the experimental impedance data of the lithium-ion battery at the four state of charge (SOC) levels (94.73 %, 89.47 %, 78.95 % and 68.42 %) and at three ambient temperatures (0 °C, 10 °C and 25 °C). Root Mean Square Errors in the case of real and imaginary part of battery impedance were lower than 1.5 Ω and 0.75 Ω, respectively. It was observed that impedance changes as a function of both temperature and SOC. Identifying different reasons for impedance changes can be of great importance in optimized battery storage or regular exploitation. Finally, the estimation method was deployed on a microcontroller with 8 kB of SRAM and a clock speed of 16 MHz, and the parameters were estimated in just 7.5 s.

1. Introduction

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) is widely used in various industrial applications [1–3]. Some examples include material analysis (monitoring of metal corrosion or material fatigue) [4], performance analysis of electrochemical sources (state of health-SOH or state of charge-SOC estimations) [5,6] or electrochemical sources degradation [7], analysis of polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) fuel cell instabilities [8], investigation of relaxation time of lithium-ion batteries [9], etc. EIS is also used in the development of the biomedical devices and body composition analyzers [10]. Modeling of measured electrical impedance with equivalent electrical circuits is a very important aspect of EIS. The comprehension of underlying processes becomes possible since elements of the equivalent electrical circuit mimic some of the physical or electrochemical processes. Therefore, monitoring the changes of model parameters can enable the recognition of the source for obtained change in electrical impedance. For example, impedance of the human body can vary due to water fluctuations, cell aging, diseases, and similar. Impedance of electrochemical sources (e.g.,

lithium-ion battery) can vary because of SOC or SOH changes, environmental temperature fluctuations, or structural damages. The EIS also enables the analysis of charge transfer interactions at electrode-electrolyte interfaces. Additionally, it allows the determination of Faradic impedance related to both charge transfer and diffusional processes in supercapacitors [11]. EIS can also differentiate among various physical phenomena taking place at distinct time scales within fuel cells, without causing damage [12], or provide valuable insights into the electrochemical processes occurring within fuel cells, such as electrode kinetics and ion transport, which is of importance for diagnostic aspects [13]. EIS proves effective as an in-situ method for capturing polarization processes with specific time constants in PEM fuel cells [14]. Furthermore, it was feasible to measure the resistance related to charge transport and the duration of electron activity across different molar ratios and varying film thicknesses in solar cells [15].

Electrical impedance measurement involves applying an alternating current (AC) signal, either voltage or current, to the electrochemical system over a range of frequencies. The system's response, comprising both amplitude and phase of current or voltage, is then recorded.

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Assuming a linear and time-invariant system, electrical impedance can be calculated. Various methods exist to analyze the amplitude and phase of both excitation and response signals. These methods, for example, can be categorized based on whether transient-state or steady-state measurements are utilized [16]. Furthermore, techniques such as employing a gain phase detector (GPD), IQ demodulation, and fast Fourier transform (FFT) [17] have been identified as appropriate methods for conducting impedance calculations in EIS [18].

Efficient impedance processing and parameter estimation for equivalent electrical circuits is a topic of great interest in scientific communities. Among various equivalent electrical circuits, the Cole-impedance model [19] is mentioned as possible adequate solution for modeling of impedance of the human body [20], fruits [21], vegetables [22], batteries [23]–[25]. The Cole-impedance model consists of four parameters (R_∞ , R_0 , C and α) organized in an electrical configuration where resistance R_∞ is connected in series with resistor R_0 connected in parallel with a constant phase element (CPE) (modelled with capacitor C and non-dimensional parameter α), as later shown in Subsection 2.1. Here should be noted that the Cole-impedance model usually can be applied only in mid-frequency range to fit EIS behavior (corresponding to a semi ellipse observed on the Nyquist diagram). In the case of wider frequency range, a more complex equivalent circuit might be required to include high frequency inductive effect and low frequency diffusion phenomenon. The decision if the Cole-impedance model is suitable should be made in compliance with the conducted analysis: if there is a small fitting error followed by the correlation of changes in model parameters and battery operational conditions (as discussed in Subsection 2.8). Examples of criteria for fitting evaluation are presented in Subsection 2.6. An error analysis is an off-line procedure for validation of the model adopted. Once the model is validated, then the approach is to obtain the parameters which would be within the accuracy range as evidenced by error analysis.

The presence of the empirical element (CPE) in the Cole-impedance model introduces the need for advanced estimation methods that are capable of estimating four model parameters from the measured data [26]. Reported approaches for parameter estimation of the Cole-impedance model are based on non-linear least squares (NLLS) [27,28] or metaheuristic optimization approaches (MOA) [29–31], which are usually implemented on a Personal Computer (PC)-based configuration. Efficient implementations of NLLS and MOA usually need a specific function or toolbox that are available only within certain PC based software packages. In addition to the specialized software, such an approach requires trained personnel for software configuration and data processing. For example, NLLS solvers, based on trust region reflective or Levenberg Marquardt algorithms, require initial values of model parameters provided by the user for starting the estimation. Moreover, step size, termination and evaluation tolerances must be defined properly as well. Otherwise, the estimation method will not converge to the global solution, making this process very difficult for unexperienced users. Because of that, the development of new estimation methods that will eliminate above mentioned limitations is still an emerging field.

Our work's primary contribution lies in the technique we developed for estimating parameters in the Cole-impedance model (Subsection 2.2), without any actions made by the user, other than selecting the frequency range of the data for analysis. Such an approach can be an integral part of various industrial processes where monitoring of electrochemical sources is needed. The presented method performs parameter estimation from EIS data that can be obtained with any impedance measurement device. Our method has been first validated using synthetic datasets, and by comparison with the relevant references (Subsections 3.1 and 3.2).

The presented estimation approach is specifically tailored for parameter estimation in the case of single dispersion Cole-impedance model. However, under certain conditions, it can also be employed for the parameter estimation of the double dispersion Cole-impedance model, as discussed in Subsection 3.3. As an illustrative example of

our method's suitability for electrochemical source monitoring, impedance of 2.9 Ah Panasonic 18650PF cell was measured at four SOC levels in a thermal chamber (three environmental temperatures). Obtained impedance was fitted to the Cole-impedance model with the proposed method, as it was shown in Subsection 3.4. The proposed estimation method is also compared against the relevant works reported earlier in the literature. Our primary contribution lies in the fact that our method does not necessitate the use of particular software functions or toolboxes, nor does it rely on user-defined initial values. This is exemplified by implementing the method on a 8-bit microcontroller (Subsection 3.5).

2. Methods

2.1. The Cole-impedance model

The electrical impedance of the Cole-impedance model at angular frequency ω_i is given with:

$$\underline{Z}(\omega_i) = R(\omega_i) + jX(\omega_i) = R_\infty + \frac{R_0 - R_\infty}{1 + (R_0 - R_\infty)C(j\omega_i)^\alpha} \quad (1)$$

where i is an integer varying from 1 to N and the number of impedance measurement points is N . The four parameters of the Cole-impedance model are R_∞ , R_0 , C and α . R_∞ (the high-frequency resistance) signifies the purely ohmic resistance component of the system (when there is no charge transfer or relaxation processes occurring). R_0 is the low-frequency resistance that characterizes the system's inherent resistance in the absence of any frequency-dependent effects. The CPE element (C and α) is often used to model non-ideal behaviors in electrochemical systems due to surface roughness, porous electrodes, or other complexities/inhomogeneities. Parameter α is in the range $[0,1]$, while other parameters are positive, but without strict range limits.

The real part of (1), or resistance $R(\omega_i)$, is given with:

$$R(\omega_i) = R_\infty + \frac{(R_0 - R_\infty) \left(1 + \omega_i^\alpha \cos \frac{\alpha\pi}{2} (R_0 - R_\infty) C \right)}{\left(1 + \omega_i^\alpha \cos \frac{\alpha\pi}{2} (R_0 - R_\infty) C \right)^2 + \left(\omega_i^\alpha \sin \frac{\alpha\pi}{2} (R_0 - R_\infty) C \right)^2} \quad (2)$$

while the imaginary part, or reactance, is given with:

$$X(\omega_i) = \frac{-\left(\omega_i^\alpha \sin \frac{\alpha\pi}{2} (R_0 - R_\infty) C \right)}{\left(1 + \omega_i^\alpha \cos \frac{\alpha\pi}{2} (R_0 - R_\infty) C \right)^2 + \left(\omega_i^\alpha \sin \frac{\alpha\pi}{2} (R_0 - R_\infty) C \right)^2} \quad (3)$$

The characteristic angular frequency ω_c of (1), which is equal to the reciprocal values of the relaxation constant, can be calculated with:

$$\omega_c = \frac{1}{((R_0 - R_\infty)C)^{1/\alpha}} \quad (4)$$

The structure of the equivalent circuit of the Cole-impedance model is shown in Fig. 1(a), while the typical Nyquist plot is shown in Fig. 1(b).

2.2. The proposed estimation method

Our estimation method starts with processing the measured impedance by estimating the characteristic angular frequency $\hat{\omega}_c$ as the frequency where the absolute value of reactance array has the maximum. This can be achieved with a very convenient procedure that starts by declaring the first element of the array as the maximum. Maximum value is then compared with the array elements from the second element till the end, and if the current element has a higher value than the maximum, the current element becomes new maximum. This method is also known as Linear Search Algorithm. Another approach can be Divide and Conquer Algorithm, which belongs to the group of recursive methods.

The value of reactance at the characteristic angular frequency is

Fig. 1. (a) The equivalent electrical circuit of Cole-impedance model, (b) the Nyquist plot, and (c) the flowchart of the proposed estimation method.

labelled with X_c , while the corresponding value of resistance is labelled with R_c . Values of R_c and X_c can be calculated with eqs. (5) and (6), respectively, which are derived from Eq. (1):

$$R_c = R(\hat{\omega}_c) = R_\infty + \frac{R_0 - R_\infty}{2} \quad (5)$$

$$X_c = X(\hat{\omega}_c) = \frac{-(R_0 - R_\infty) \sin \frac{\alpha\pi}{2}}{2(1 + \cos \frac{\alpha\pi}{2})} = -\frac{(R_0 - R_\infty)}{2} \tan \frac{\alpha\pi}{4} \quad (6)$$

Assuming that characteristic frequency is estimated from measured reactance, with procedure described above, the value on the left side of Eq. (4) is known. Moreover, values of R_c and X_c are also available from the measured values. Therefore, by combining the eqs. (4)–(6), it is possible to estimate values of R_∞, R_0, C if α is known:

$$\hat{R}_\infty = R_c + X_c \frac{(1 + \cos \frac{\alpha\pi}{2})}{\sin \frac{\alpha\pi}{2}} = R_c + \frac{X_c}{\tan \frac{\alpha\pi}{4}} \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{R}_0 = R_c - X_c \frac{(1 + \cos \frac{\alpha\pi}{2})}{\sin \frac{\alpha\pi}{2}} = R_c - \frac{X_c}{\tan \frac{\alpha\pi}{4}} \quad (8)$$

$$\hat{C} = \frac{-\sin \frac{\alpha\pi}{2}}{2X_c \hat{\omega}_c^\alpha (1 + \cos \frac{\alpha\pi}{2})} = \frac{\tan \frac{\alpha\pi}{4}}{2X_c \hat{\omega}_c^\alpha} \quad (9)$$

Our approach is to solve Eqs. (7)–(9) for various values of α in range $[0,1]$ with certain step, and to keep value for α that will minimize the error between measured (R and X) and fitted (R_{est} and X_{est}) impedance data:

$$\arg \min_{\alpha} \left\{ \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\Delta R(\alpha, \omega_i)}{R(\omega_i)} + \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\Delta X(\alpha, \omega_i)}{X(\omega_i)} \right\} \quad (10)$$

where

$$\Delta R(\alpha, \omega_i) = |R_{est}(\alpha, \omega_i) - R(\omega_i)| \quad (11)$$

and

$$\Delta X(\alpha, \omega_i) = |X_{est}(\alpha, \omega_i) - X(\omega_i)| \quad (12)$$

The simplest way is to start with $\alpha = 0$ and to apply linear step $\Delta\alpha$ to

increase values of α towards 1. However, through a series of iterative calculations, it is feasible to determine an initial value of α using larger increments (e.g., 0.1). Once this value (α_1) is obtained, a finer calculation can be performed using smaller increments (e.g., 0.01) within a narrower range around α_1 . Subsequently, employing even smaller increments (e.g., 0.001) within a more focused range around the intermediate value (α_2) allows for the final determination of α with a precision of 0.1%. The optimal value of α will be selected based on the minimal value calculated using Eq. (10). As previously mentioned, the parameters in the Cole impedance model must be positive values. Examining Eqs. (7)–(9), it becomes evident that there exists a minimum value for parameter α , ensuring that the remaining model parameters remain non-negative:

$$\alpha > -\frac{4}{\pi} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{X(\hat{\omega}_c)}{R(\hat{\omega}_c)} \right) = \alpha_{init} \quad (13)$$

Consequently, rather than initializing α with zero, starting with this minimum value that guarantees physically valid values for the other parameters can speed up the estimation process. The flowchart of the proposed estimation method is shown in Fig. 1(c).

2.3. Used software and hardware systems

The PC-based estimations with the presented method were performed using MATLAB 2013b installed on the Dell G5 laptop. The supplementary materials of this manuscript contain programming code (Main_script.m) used for the obtaining of the presented results. Moreover, the MATLAB script for the generation of synthetic datasets is also provided (Data_generation.m).

The validation of the proposed estimation method with embedded hardware was done using the Arduino Mega2560 board, while the program code was written in Arduino IDE 1.8.5.

2.4. Used datasets

Initially, synthetic datasets were created using nominal values of model parameters ($R_\infty = 84.40 \Omega$, $R_0 = 123.60 \Omega$, $C = 2.31 \mu\text{F} \cdot \text{s}^{\alpha-1}$ and $\alpha = 0.747$) and Eq. (1). The corresponding characteristic frequency and angular characteristic frequency are as follows: $f_c = 41,161.65 \text{ Hz}$ and $\omega_c = 258,495.16 \text{ rad/s}$, respectively. Nominal values of model

parameters, frequency range from 3 kHz to 1 MHz, with $N = 256$ logarithmically spaced points, were used to ensure comparison with relevant work [28]. Used frequency range and number of measurement points are also typical for commercial devices, such as ImpediMed SFB7. In addition to the noiseless dataset, a dataset with random noise added to resistance and reactance was also created. Adding random noise to resistance and reactance values is a straightforward method that is easy to implement, enabling analyses within a reasonable timeframe. Simulations with random noise become more realistic and applicable to practical scenarios due to the stochastic nature of real-world data. More importantly, the intensity and distribution of the noise added to the data can be controlled. Therefore, effects of different noise levels can be studied, leading to a better understanding of the estimation method's performances under varying conditions. In our work, the level of noise was managed by employing a random number generation function called *rng*. A commonly used pseudorandom number generator known as *Mersenne Twister* was specified for this purpose. The MATLAB script for the generation of synthetic datasets is provided as the supplementary material (Data_generation.m), enabling the reproducibility of the obtained results and further improvements of the proposed method. The noise level gradually increased from 0 % (noiseless) to 5 %. Random noise with level of 0.25 % was interesting for the comparison with the reference [28]. The supplementary materials of this manuscript contain synthetic datasets (EIS_synthetic_datasets.xlsx) used for the validation of the proposed method in Subsection 3.1. The need for the more complex analysis of the noise impact on equivalent electrical circuits, due to frequency-dependent nature of noise (broadband and narrowband), is recognized in [32]. Performance evaluation of our proposed estimation method with random and varied frequency components (broadband noise), as well as narrowband noise characterized by having energy concentrated within a limited frequency range is a possible direction for further developments of the proposed estimation method.

As the validation part of the proposed estimation method with experimentally obtained impedance data from a real-life object, we used publicly available dataset of Li-ion battery impedance measurements [33]. Impedance of 2.9 Ah Panasonic 18650PF cell was measured in a thermal chamber with a Digatron Firing Circuits Universal Battery Tester. Frequency range was from 100 mHz to 6 kHz. Measured values at four SOC levels (94.73 %, 89.47 %, 78.95 % and 68.42 %) and three environmental temperatures (0 °C, 10 °C and 25 °C) were used. The actual frequency range that was fitted to the Cole-impedance model was determined manually by observing the Nyquist plots of measured values, and its coincidence with the expected depressed semicircle. We also see the opportunity in the further development of the study, to include machine learning methods that will analyze the input impedance dataset. For example, classifications if it is expected that dataset corresponds to the Cole-impedance model, or frequency trimming is needed. Another possibility is to analyze the first derivative of resistance, reactance, or reactance with respect to resistance to reveal if there is the expected extremum as it is visible on the Nyquist plot. These methods can potentially eliminate the need for user selection of the frequency range, which will be further investigated in our future work.

2.5. Sensitivity and selectivity studies

Measured impedance that can be modelled with the Cole-impedance model is, in general, a function of four parameters: $Z = \text{fun}(R_\infty, R_0, C, \alpha)$, as described with Eq. (1). The reliability of the proposed estimation method to distinguish which parameter caused the observed change in impedance was also analyzed. This was done using the synthetic dataset ($R_\infty = 84.40 \Omega$, $R_0 = 123.60 \Omega$, $C = 2.31 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$ and $\alpha = 0.747$) and repeated estimations with change of just one parameter for 1 %, 5 % and finally 10 %, while other parameters remain constant. The described procedure was then repeated for each parameter.

This part of the study is important because it enables the impedance change to be linked to various underlying processes.

2.6. Evaluation of parameter estimation

In case of synthetic datasets, the reference values of model parameters are available, thus it was possible to compare estimated and reference values with a relative error (RE) calculation:

$$RE(\%) = \frac{|Estimated - Reference|}{Reference} \times 100\% \quad (14)$$

Reference values are not defined in the case of the experimentally obtained impedance of the electrochemical sensors or sources, such as batteries. Because of that, we calculated root mean square errors (RMSE) between measured (R and X) and estimated (R_{est} and X_{est}) values of real and imaginary part of impedance

$$RMSE(R) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (R_{est}(i) - R(i))^2} \quad (15)$$

$$RMSE(X) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_{est}(i) - X(i))^2} \quad (16)$$

The FIT(%), which does not depend on reactance and resistance magnitude, was also calculated with:

$$FIT(\%) = \left(1 - \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N ((R_{est}(i) - R(i))^2 + (X_{est}(i) - X(i))^2)}{\sum_{i=1}^N ((R_{est}(i) - \bar{R})^2 + (X_{est}(i) - \bar{X})^2)}}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (17)$$

where \bar{R} and \bar{X} are the mean values of resistance $R(i)$ and reactance values $X(i)$.

In addition to that, relative errors between measured and estimated resistance and reactance are determined to evaluate the frequential distribution of the error modeling:

$$\Delta_{re}(\%) = \frac{R(f) - R_{est}(f)}{\sqrt{(R^2(f) + X^2(f))^2}} \times 100\% \quad (18)$$

$$\Delta_{im}(\%) = \frac{X(f) - X_{est}(f)}{\sqrt{(R^2(f) + X^2(f))^2}} \times 100\% \quad (19)$$

We introduced a Pearson correlation coefficient (it ranges from -1 to 1) as a measure how the changes of model parameters correspond to changes in values of battery SOC and temperature:

$$r = \frac{\text{Covariance}(p_1, p_2)}{SD(p_1) \times SD(p_2)} \quad (20)$$

where each set of model parameter (R_∞ , R_0 , C and α) values will be used as p_1 , while temperature and SOC values will be p_2 .

2.7. The applicability of the proposed estimation method on other equivalent electrical circuits

Depending on the value of α , the CPE can have a different physical interpretation. For example, if $\alpha = 0$ then CPE represents the resistor, while it is an ideal capacitor if $\alpha = 1$. In addition to this boundary interpretations, if $\alpha = 0.5$ then CPE has a phase angle of $-\pi/4$, and it is called Warburg impedance. The proposed estimation method can also be used on different equivalent electrical circuits with the same topology in which CPE is replaced by the ideal capacitor or Warburg impedance.

It is also possible that, in the analyzed frequency range, there are multiple processes in the battery that cannot be accurately described with the single dispersion Cole-impedance model. In that case, extension of the equivalent electrical circuit is required. For example, addition of

the second parallel branch composed of resistor and CPE might be needed, as shown in Fig. 3. Our estimation method is derived and optimized for the single dispersion Cole-impedance model, and it cannot be directly applied for the parameter estimation of the double dispersion Cole-impedance model. However, in some cases it would be possible to separate impedance data if the two semi-circles are distinctive (they are not overlapping), and to apply our estimation method of two single dispersion models. In cases when the contributions of Cole-impedance model elements are not limited to a very distinct frequency range and they do contribute to the impedance on other frequencies as well, the proposed estimation method cannot be applied. One can see this as the drawback of the proposed work, but the achieved optimizations in terms of fast execution, high accuracy, low complexity, and suitability for the independent microcontroller-based operation makes this method of great importance for applications in which the single dispersion Cole-impedance model can be applied.

2.8. The importance of the proposed estimation method of the Cole-impedance model for battery monitoring

The proposed estimation method is of importance for general EIS, as the Cole-impedance model is extensively used in numerous applications. Moreover, among others, as discussed in the Introduction section, EIS and the Cole-impedance model found applications in overall battery characterization [24], aging monitoring [25], analysis of the operation conditions impact on high-power lithium-ion batteries [34]. Monitoring of equivalent electrical circuit elements was found to be appropriate solution for monitoring of Li-ion battery variation in terms of temperature and SOC when exposed to aging [35].

In this paper we present a new method which will be beneficial to researchers more focused on the battery analysis, since the proposed method enables reliable parameter extraction that will be helpful in process of making correlation of changes in model parameters and battery operational conditions. For example, an increase in electrolyte resistance may be a sign of battery electrolyte deterioration or contamination. Alterations in the battery's diffusion properties, such as changes in porosity, electrode deterioration, or electrolyte depletion, may also be reflected in the changes. Moreover, changes in the capacitance may be a sign of modifications to the electrode's surface area, morphology, or interactions with the electrolyte.

For some analysis, such as Li-ion battery performance indications, it is very common to use Cole-impedance model in the modified form, which includes use of $R_{ct} = R_0 - R_\infty$ and $\tau_c = (R_{ct}C)^{1/\alpha}$ in Eq. (1), which becomes:

$$\underline{Z}(\omega_i) = R_\infty + \frac{R_{ct}}{1 + (\tau_c j \omega_i)^\alpha} \quad (21)$$

Parameters of R_{ct} and τ_c can be easily calculated using the estimated values with the proposed method. In case of Li-ion battery, R_∞ stands for the electrolyte and connection resistance, R_{ct} stands for the charge transfer resistance and τ_c characterizes the charge transfer dynamics. Parameters R_{ct} and τ_c could be used as performance indicators as they are dependent on SOC.

Table 1

Estimated values of model parameters and relative errors (RE) for different noise levels.

Noise level	\hat{R}_∞ (Ω)	$RE(\hat{R}_\infty)$	\hat{R}_0 (Ω)	$RE(\hat{R}_0)$	\hat{C} ($\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$)	$RE(\hat{C})$	$\hat{\alpha}$	$RE(\hat{\alpha})$
0 %	84.38	0.018 %	123.58	0.012 %	2.31	0.106 %	0.747	<0.0005 %
0.25 %	84.45	0.061 %	123.07	0.429 %	2.00	13.519 %	0.757	1.339 %
0.50 %	84.69	0.348 %	123.34	0.209 %	1.97	14.661 %	0.758	1.473 %
1.00 %	85.14	0.882 %	123.92	0.257 %	1.94	15.994 %	0.759	1.606 %
2.00 %	86.05	1.951 %	125.07	1.189 %	1.88	18.592 %	0.761	1.874 %
5 %	88.96	5.403 %	128.32	3.818 %	1.60	30.538 %	0.773	3.481 %

3. Results and discussion

3.1. The synthetic datasets

Estimated values in case on noiseless dataset and datasets with different levels (0 %, 0.25 %, 0.50 %, 1.00 %, 2.00 % and 5 %) of noise are summarized in Table 1. It should be noted that all results were obtained when noisy datasets were not filtered. This was done with the purpose of characterizing the actual response of the proposed estimation method when noise is present in the input data (which is expected in real-life applications). Relative errors are lower than 0.106 % in case of the noiseless impedance data. With increasing noise estimated resistance error stays relatively low but error for estimated C is as much as 30 %. However, the relative error in estimation of the corresponding characteristic frequency is 0.092 % in case of the noiseless dataset, while all noise levels greater than zero a 4.757 % was obtained.

Comparison (Nyquist plots) between the reference and estimated impedance data are shown in Fig. 2. Calculated RMSE values for resistance and reactance are also shown in Fig. 2.

It is worth mentioning that $FIT(\%)$ values, calculated using (17), decreased from 99.93 % for the noiseless data, to 97.75 % for 0.25 % noise level, 96.09 % for 0.50 % noise level, 91.78 % for 1.00 % noise level, 82.93 % for 2.00 % noise level and just 58.96 % for 5.00 % noise level. Low $FIT(\%)$ value is not surprising in case of 5 % noise level, because the actual input data deviates from the expected curve, while the corresponding fitted data follows the Cole-impedance equation. It should be noted that slightly different results can be obtained for the same noise level depending on the realization.

Degradation of the estimation performances with the increasing noise levels lead to application of the moving average filter to filter noisy reactance data. A moving average filter is a simple signal processing technique that calculates the average of a sequence of data points within a fixed window. Output results are strongly dependent on window size and the most common approach is trial and error. However, the low-complexity of the moving average filter is suitable for the microcontroller-based implementation. In this work, the window size was set to 3 in case of 5 % noise level. Relative errors in the parameter estimations decreased from 5.403 %, 3.818 %, 30.538 % and 3.481 % (as shown in Table 1) to 0.107 %, 0.157 %, 18.782 % and 2.008 % for R , R_0 , C and α , respectively. RMSEs also decreased from $RMSE(R) = 5.769 \Omega$ and $RMSE(X) = 0.480 \Omega$ to $RMSE(R) = 2.995 \Omega$ and $RMSE(X) = 0.283 \Omega$. Finally, it should be noted that $FIT(\%)$ increased from 58.96 % to 76.87 %, clearly indicating an improvement in the goodness of fitting. Therefore, even with the moving average filter is possible to improve the estimation accuracy of the proposed estimation method. Further optimizations of the moving average filter for the integration with the estimation method will be part of our future work.

3.2. The results of sensitivity and selectivity studies

Comparison of reference and estimated values in sensitivity and selectivity studies are summarized in Table 2. The proposed estimation method is highly selective to specific changes of each model parameter. Moreover, it can be noticed that high sensitivity (1 % changes) is obtained.

Fig. 2. Nyquist plots of reference and estimated data for different noise levels.

3.3. The parameter estimation of the double dispersion Cole-impedance model

As described in Subsection 2.7, the proposed estimation method is optimized for the parameter estimation of the single dispersion Cole-impedance model, but it can be applied to the double dispersion Cole-impedance model if it is possible to separate impedance data (two semi-circles are distinctive and they are not overlapping). In such a case, our estimation method can be applied to two single dispersion models. As an example, reference values of model parameters are taken from [36]: $R_{\infty} = 42.9 \Omega$, $R_1 = 71.6 \Omega$, $R_2 = 16.5 \Omega$, $C_1 = 3.086 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha_1}$, $C_2 = 89.29 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha_2}$, $\alpha_1 = 0.507$ and $\alpha_2 = 0.766$. Frequency range from 10 Hz to 25 MHz is divided with 50 logarithmically spaced points. Equivalent electrical circuit and the Nyquist plot (solid red line) of double dispersion Cole-impedance model are shown in Fig. 3.

Input dataset was divided into two subsets: (S1) frequency range from 24.2 kHz to 25 MHz, and (S2) frequency range from 10 Hz to 10.072 kHz. The corresponding values of two single dispersion Cole-impedance model parameters were extracted: $R_{\infty,1} = 43.61 \Omega$, $R_{0,1} = 116.71 \Omega$, $C_1 = 3.75 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha_1}$ and $\alpha_1 = 0.498$ for S1; $R_{\infty,2} = 111.37 \Omega$, $R_{0,2} = 131.07 \Omega$, $C_2 = 8.07 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha_2}$ and $\alpha_2 = 0.745$ for S2. The final values

of model parameters are as follows: $R_{\infty} = R_{\infty,1} = 43.61 \Omega$, $R_1 = R_{0,1} - R_{\infty,1} = 73.10 \Omega$, $C_1 = 3.75 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha_1}$, $\alpha_1 = 0.498$, $R_2 = R_{0,2} - R_{0,1} = 14.35 \Omega$, $C_2 = 8.07 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha_2}$ and $\alpha_2 = 0.745$. The corresponding RMSE values for the real and imaginary part were 1.635 Ω and 0.713 Ω , respectively, while *FIT*(%) value was calculated to be 92.16%. Fig. 3(b) contains Nyquist plot of estimated values (blue dashed line). The frequential distributions of errors for resistance and reactance remained within the range of $\pm 3\%$ for the entire frequency range, as shown in Fig. 3(c).

3.4. The experimentally obtained impedance: Battery datasets

Estimated values of Cole-impedance model of battery at three environmental temperatures and four SOC values are summarized in Table 3.

Nyquist plots of measured and estimated battery impedance data are shown in Fig. 4- Fig. 6. As it can be seen in given figures, the Cole-impedance model and the proposed estimation methods provide a very good fitting results, with RMSEs in case of real and imaginary part of battery impedance lower than 1.5 Ω and 0.75 Ω , respectively.

In case of battery impedance, two analyses can be performed [37]. Firstly, the impact of temperature changes with constant SOC, which can be important for storage process. Secondly, SOC changes at constant

Table 2
Sensitivity and selectivity study: estimated values of model parameters.

Label		\hat{R}_∞ (Ω)	\hat{R}_0 (Ω)	\hat{C} ($\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$)	$\hat{\alpha}$
Initial	Reference	84.40	123.60	2.31	0.747
	Estimated	84.38	123.58	2.31	0.747
$R_\infty + 1\%$	Reference	85.24	123.60	2.31	0.747
	Estimated	85.26	123.68	2.34	0.746
$R_\infty + 5\%$	Reference	88.62	123.60	2.31	0.747
	Estimated	88.60	123.46	2.25	0.749
$R_\infty + 10\%$	Reference	92.84	123.60	2.31	0.747
	Estimated	92.88	123.63	2.32	0.747
$R_0 + 1\%$	Reference	84.40	124.84	2.31	0.747
	Estimated	84.43	124.86	2.31	0.747
$R_0 + 5\%$	Reference	84.40	129.78	2.31	0.747
	Estimated	84.42	129.95	2.37	0.745
$R_0 + 10\%$	Reference	84.40	135.96	2.31	0.747
	Estimated	84.39	135.86	2.28	0.748
$C + 1\%$	Reference	84.40	123.60	2.33	0.747
	Estimated	84.42	123.75	2.40	0.745
$C + 5\%$	Reference	84.40	123.60	2.43	0.747
	Estimated	84.42	123.62	2.43	0.747
$C + 10\%$	Reference	84.40	123.60	2.54	0.747
	Estimated	84.41	123.75	2.61	0.745
$\alpha + 1\%$	Reference	84.40	123.60	2.31	0.754
	Estimated	84.37	123.40	2.23	0.757
$\alpha + 5\%$	Reference	84.40	123.60	2.31	0.784
	Estimated	84.39	123.55	2.29	0.785
$\alpha + 10\%$	Reference	84.40	123.60	2.31	0.822
	Estimated	84.44	123.68	2.33	0.821

temperature are of importance for battery operation. Using estimated values of Cole-impedance model, it can be observed that, at constant SOC values, decrease of temperature starting from 25 °C over 10 °C to 0

°C lead to increase of R_∞ and R_0 values, while value of C decreased. Parameter α decreased with temperature decrease from 25 °C to 10 °C, but then increased during the change from 10 °C to 0 °C. At all three values of constant temperature, decreasing of SOC lead to decrease of parameters R_∞ , R_0 and α , while values of C fluctuated around very similar value equal to the first SOC value.

From Figs. 4–6, it can be noticed that there is a change in the frequency range that was included in the fitting. This can be explained by changes in battery electrical properties due to changes in SOC and temperature. For example, SOC and temperature have influence on ion mobility, the solid-electrolyte interface thickness, changes in the crystalline structure, the viscosity of the electrolyte, different speed of kinetic reactions, changes in electrode conductivity, etc. The corresponding model parameters, that for example, represent series electrolyte resistance, charge transfer resistance or double layer capacitance, will also change. Consequently, the characteristic frequency will also change, which will shift the reactance peak within the Nyquist plot. It is evident that application of the Cole-impedance model with small fitting error will require different narrower frequency ranges where the same phenomena is covered. However, small fitting errors should not be the only criterion, because a good correlation between changes of values of model parameters and observed physical phenomena is also required. Application of machine learning techniques, such as a gradient-boosted tree model, to classify if input impedance data can be fitted with the Cole-impedance model, is a possible extension of our work. It was recently demonstrated that automatic classification of suitability of the equivalent electrical circuit to fit impedance dataset is possible [38].

In the case of the results shown in Table 3 and Figs. 4–6, the calculations of correlation coefficients, using Eq. (20), between changes of model parameters and changes in SOC/temperature, indicates that R_∞

Fig. 3. (a) The equivalent electrical circuit of the double dispersion Cole-impedance model, (b) the Nyquist plots of reference and estimated values, (c) frequential distributions of errors for resistance and reactance.

Table 3
Estimated values of model parameters for different battery SOC and environmental temperatures.

SOC (%)	\hat{R}_∞ (Ω)			\hat{R}_0 (Ω)			\hat{C} ($\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$)			$\hat{\alpha}$		
	0 °C	10 °C	25 °C	0 °C	10 °C	25 °C	0 °C	10 °C	25 °C	0 °C	10 °C	25 °C
94.73	38.14	30.74	23.73	109.04	80.04	42.28	3.90	3.99	4.63	0.80	0.85	0.80
89.47	36.60	29.48	22.77	96.80	63.03	36.70	4.15	4.40	6.17	0.73	0.77	0.68
78.95	31.89	22.83	21.07	81.52	54.26	31.85	3.99	5.70	5.93	0.65	0.52	0.58
68.42	34.36	20.83	20.78	79.45	53.03	31.16	3.85	6.09	6.18	0.71	0.45	0.54

Fig. 4. Nyquist plots of measured and estimated battery impedance at temperature of 0 °C and varying SOC.

Fig. 5. Nyquist plots of measured and estimated battery impedance at temperature of 10 °C and varying SOC.

Fig. 6. Nyquist plots of measured and estimated battery impedance at temperature of 25 °C and varying SOC.

Fig. 7. FIT(%) values and the frequential distributions of errors for resistance and reactance at different battery SOC and environmental temperatures.

correlates 0.97 with SOC decrease from 94.73 % to 68.42 % at 10 °C, and 0.95 at 25 °C. R_∞ also showed high and negative correlations (-0.99 , -0.99 , -0.88 and -0.81) with temperature increase from 0 °C to 25 °C at 94.73 %, 89.47 %, 78.95 % and 68.42 SOC values, respectively. On the other hand, R_0 showed even higher negative correlations (-0.99 , -0.98 , -0.99 and -0.99) with temperature increase from 0 °C to 25 °C at 94.73 %, 89.47 %, 78.95 % and 68.42 % SOC values, respectively. R_0 also correlates very well with SOC decrease from 94.73 % to 68.42 % at the constant temperature: 0.94 (0 °C), 0.88 (10 °C) and 0.92 (25 °C). Parameter C showed positive correlation with temperature increase from 0 °C to 25 °C at all four SOC values: 0.96 (94.73 %), 0.96 (89.47 %), 0.86 (78.95 %) and 0.83 (68.42 %). Finally, the parameter α showed positive correlation with SOC increase at 10 °C (0.97) and 25 °C (0.95).

In addition to the RMSEs, shown in Figs. 4–6, the performed estimations were evaluated in terms of $FIT(\%)$, given with Eq. (17), as well as the frequential distributions of errors for resistance and reactance, given with Eq. (18) and (19), respectively. Calculated $FIT(\%)$ values and the frequential distributions of errors for resistance and reactance at different battery SOC and environmental temperatures are shown in Fig. 7.

$FIT(\%)$ values are higher than 90 % for the majority of the analyzed datasets. Additional validation of the proposed estimation method was confirmed with the frequential distributions of errors for resistance and reactance that remain within the range of ± 4 % for the entire frequency range of the specific dataset.

3.5. The microcontroller-based implementation of the proposed estimation method

The suitability of the proposed method for the deployment on the low-cost microcontroller board is demonstrated with the deployment on the Mega2560 board. It is based on the ATmega2560 microcontroller with 256 kB of flash memory and 8 kB of SRAM. The clock speed is

16 MHz. The only parameter that has impact on the estimation speed is the step size of α , which can be defined as the compromise between the estimation time and accuracy. We firstly analyzed performances for step sizes of 0.01 and 0.001.

Estimated value with α -step size equal to 0.01 were: $\hat{R}_\infty=84.55 \Omega$, $\hat{R}_0=122.97 \Omega$, $\hat{C}=1.93 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$ and $\hat{\alpha}=0.76$. The program code requires 9796 of available 253,952 bytes of the flash memory, while 4464 of 8192 SRAM bytes is used. The estimation time was 16.33 s.

The higher estimation accuracy was achieved with the α -step size equal to 0.001 as estimated values were: $\hat{R}_\infty=84.45 \Omega$, $\hat{R}_0=123.07 \Omega$, $\hat{C}=2.00 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$ and $\hat{\alpha}=0.757$. However, such a realization required 162.89 s.

With the multi-step estimations, it is possible to find initial value for α with step of 0.1. If that value is marked as α_1 , then smaller step (0.01 for example) can be applied in the range from $\alpha_1-0.1$ to $\alpha_1+0.1$ which will result with value of α_2 . Finally, the step of 0.001 can be applied in the range $\alpha_2-0.01$ to $\alpha_2+0.01$ to find the final value of α with the resolution of 0.1 %. For the given dataset, the value for $\alpha_1 = 0.8$ was obtained after 1.51 s, followed $\alpha_2 = 0.76$ after 4.29 s, and finally $\alpha = 0.757$ in just 7.24 s.

The microcontroller-based implementation offers an advantage because it allows for in-situ parameter estimation. Moreover, graphical comparison between measured and estimated values is possible at the measurement spot, as shown in Fig. 8. Moreover, Fig. 8 shows a host computer interface and PC-based environment for parameter estimation.

3.6. The key performance indicators of the proposed estimation method and comparison with the related work

One approach to the estimation of Cole-impedance model parameters is based on customized hardware platforms, such as that for the

Fig. 8. A host computer interface for PC-based parameter estimation, and in-situ comparison of measured and estimated values with embedded hardware (Mega2560).

Table 4
Estimated values of model parameters and execution times for different estimation methods.

	\hat{R}_∞ (Ω)	\hat{R}_0 (Ω)	\hat{C} ($\mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$)	$\hat{\alpha}$	Execution time (seconds)	Embedded hardware platform
Reference values	84.40	123.60	2.31	0.747	NA	NA
[43]	84.62	123.27	2.25	0.750	22.11	Mega2560
[44]	84.23	123.29	2.20	0.750	18.16	Mega2560
[28]	84.47	123.45	2.21	0.751	31.1	Raspberry Pi
This work	84.45	123.07	2.00	0.757	7.24	Mega2560

current step response analysis method [39]. Even though such an approach reduces the complexity of the necessary hardware, it does not contain information about measured electrical impedance in the given frequency range. Electrical impedance of many processes is frequency-dependent, which means that different equivalent circuits are needed for different frequency ranges. Moreover, the used hardware should be tuned for optimal performance and capturing of the requested three very specific time moments of interest for the given application. In many cases, this cannot be predicted, as a-priori knowledge about the process is not available. The development of the customized hardware platforms, such as oscillator tuning at two different frequencies [40] or characterization based on triangle voltage [41], bring the same limitations as time-domain estimation of the step response. Because of that, the development of software-based estimation techniques that will reduce the complexity of needed hardware for parameter estimation is also reported in the literature. For example, parameterization of raw electrical impedance data with three frequencies [42] introduced the research direction in which the development of the microcontroller-based estimation method can replace commercial systems for multi-frequency bioimpedance data fitting. However, it was shown that estimation accuracy is dependent on the selection of three frequencies. The concluding recommendation was that the selection of the most adequate frequencies should be based “to the response of the specific objects to be measured” [42].

For the effective comparison with the related works, a synthetic dataset ($R_\infty = 84.40 \Omega$, $R_0 = 123.60 \Omega$, $C = 2.31 \mu\text{F}\cdot\text{s}^{\alpha-1}$ and $\alpha = 0.747$) with 0.25 % of random noise was used. The dataset was used in two related works recently published by our research group [43,44], as well as NLLS-based approach [28]. The first approach is based on the use of measured R and X , as well as numerical approximation of the first derivative of R/X with respect to ω [43]. Implementation on the same embedded hardware platform as used in this work (Mega2560) required 16 kB of flash memory and 67 % of available RAM. The execution time was 22.11 s. Our second related work use the estimated value of the characteristic frequency, real part of impedance at the characteristic frequency and measured values of imaginary part in the complete frequency range [44]. Implementation on the Mega2560 board required 13.5 kB of flash memory and 57 % of available RAM. The execution time was 18.16 s. The NLLS-based implementation on the Raspberry Pi 3 platform is very interesting for comparison because an approach to select initial values from 100 randomly generated iterations is presented [28]. Reported estimation time is about 31 s.

The proposed estimation method and comparison with the three related works is given in Table 4. As can be seen from Table 4, the proposed method in this work is the fastest. When compared to the other two implementations on the same Mega2560 board, the proposed estimation method requires the lowest amount of flash (9.5 kB) and RAM (54.4 %).

4. Conclusion

In this paper we presented the method for the parameter extraction of the Cole-impedance model. The main contributions and some of the most important features of the proposed method are: (1) it is fully automated without any actions made by the user other than to select the

frequency range of the data to analyze, (2) it does not require initial values, such as the initial values in case of NLLS-based algorithms, (3) it does not require any special function or toolbox, and (4) it can be deployed on low-cost microcontroller boards, enabling the system integration with the existing impedance measurement systems.

The proposed method was validated using synthetic datasets and compared with the relevant work from the literature. Relative errors in the case of noiseless synthetic data were lower than 0.1 %. Moreover, impedance of Li-ion batteries obtained at different SOCs, and ambient temperatures was also successfully processed. RMSEs in case of real and imaginary part of battery impedance were lower than 1.5 Ω and 0.75 Ω , respectively. However, there are also some non-coincidences of the measured and estimated curves, which can be explained with three possible reasons: (1) estimation error of the proposed method due to the error in characteristic frequency estimation, (2) a more complex equivalent circuit might be needed for the specific operating/environmental condition, and (3) measurement process was not performed in steady state, resulting in artifacts and deviations from the expected impedance trends. Model identification and parameter identification pertain to distinct scopes of application. Here should be emphasized that the focus of this work is a novel methodology for parameter identification of the Cole-impedance model, rather than model identification. The Cole-impedance model parameters were extracted, and it was observed that, at constant SOC values, decrease of temperature lead to increase of R_∞ and R_0 values, while value of C decreased. At the constant environmental temperature, decreasing of SOC lead to decrease of parameters R_∞ , R_0 and α . Therefore, with the proposed estimation method it is possible to differentiate impedance changes caused by the different sources, which is of great importance for industrial applications in which monitoring of electrochemical sources can be provide information about the internal conditions.

Our future work will be directed towards the integration with the impedance measurement device, enabling the online parameter estimation of the Cole-impedance model in various industrial applications, such as material analysis, monitoring of electrochemical sources and bioimpedance analyzers.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mitar Simić: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Varun Jeoti:** Formal analysis, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Goran M. Stojanović:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data availability

Supplementary materials contain used datasets, while the experimental part used publicly available dataset that was referenced.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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